

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part VIII. Electrometric Titrations of Casein and Casein Fractions

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Electrometric titrations of casein and its major fractions, α - and β -caseins, using HCl as the acid and NaOH, Ca(OH)₂ or NH₄OH as the base, extending upto about pH 2.0 on the acid side and 11.2 on the alkali side, have been obtained. The α -fractions show much greater reactivity than β -fractions in the acid as well as the alkaline range while the whole casein shows intermediate behaviour, the values being close to those expected from its known composition, indicating that the major fractions lie side by side as separate entities without any significant chemical interaction with each other. The bovine products show a little higher reactivity than buffalo's products. The method of calculating the numbers of various ionic groups from such titration curves has been discussed and the values thus obtained have been shown to be in good agreement with those obtained by other workers by employing the complicated analytical techniques.

THE electrometric titrations of proteins and the applications of the same in estimating acid and base binding capacities have been reported in recent years¹⁻⁶. Similar investigations on caseins are relatively few⁷⁻⁹ and on casein fractions (e.g., α -casein and β -casein) are fewer still^{10,11}. Moreover, most of the work that is available in the literature relates only to the bovine products. There is need to extend similar work to buffalo's products as well.

Warner's observation¹², that electrophoretic mobility of α -casein decreases when mixed with β -casein, suggests the possibility of some interaction between these two major fractions of casein. However, there has been no confirmation of this view. The electrometric titrations of whole casein and its major fractions (α - and β -caseins) are expected to throw some light on the possibility of any such phenomenon. The present work was, therefore, undertaken. The alkali used for the titrations has been, hitherto, sodium hydroxide only. In the present work, calcium hydroxide and ammonium hydroxide were also used as the titrants. The acid used was the same, namely hydrochloric acid, in every case.

Experimental

Materials: Casein was isolated by Dunn's method¹³ by adding gradually 1M HCl through a dropping funnel to skim milk, diluted four times with water and kept stirred mechanically all along, till the pH value was lowered to the isoelectric point. The precipitate was washed repeatedly and fractionated into α - and β -caseins by taking advantage of their differential solubilities in urea¹⁴.

pH titration curves: Portions of casein (0.25 g) were taken in 50 ml pyrex-glass bottles and increasing amounts of 0.1N NaOH, Ca(OH)₂ or NH₄OH were added, making the volume to 25 ml in every case by the addition of 0.1N NaCl, CaCl₂ or NH₄Cl (all the

solutions were made with CO₂-free distilled water) so that the concentration of the cation was 0.1N and the ionic strength for a given titrant was the same in every bottle. Similar portions of casein were mixed with increasing amounts of 0.1N HCl and the volume was made to 25 ml in every case by the addition of 0.1N NaCl. The contents were allowed to stand, with occasional shaking, in an incubator maintained at 35 \pm 0.05 $^{\circ}$ for 48 hrs, after which they were transferred to a small beaker and kept in a thermostat maintained at the same temperature. The pH values were determined using Beckman pH-meter (glass electrode in conjunction with calomel electrode) having an accuracy of \pm 0.01 pH units. The pH values were plotted against the amounts of H⁺ or OH⁻ ion actually bound by the casein. For this purpose, the pH measured at any stage was used to calculate the concentration of free H⁺ ion (m_{H^+}) when acid was added as the titrant, or that of free OH⁻ ion (m_{OH^-}) when alkali was used as the titrant, by applying the expressions (i) or (ii):

$$(i) \text{ pH} = -\log m_{H^+} \gamma_{H^+}$$

$$(ii) \text{ pOH} = -\log m_{OH^-} \gamma_{OH^-},$$

as the case may be. Subtracting m_{H^+} or m_{OH^-} from the molality of H⁺ or OH⁻ ion added, the amount of proton or hydroxyl ion bound by casein was calculated. The values of activity coefficients at approximate concentrations were taken from the tables provided by Tanford¹⁵. The reversibility of complete titration curve (plotted on the addition of acid on one side and alkali on the other) was checked by starting with casein solution in HCl at pH 2.0 and adding increasing amounts of NaOH.

Results and Discussion

The initial pH values of the caseins and their α - and β -fractions in 1 per cent suspensions in water

or in 0.1N chloride of sodium, calcium or ammonium are presented in Table 1. The α -fraction is seen to be more acidic and β -fraction less acidic than the whole casein in the case of bovine as well as buffalo's

TABLE 1—ISOIONIC pH VALUES OF CASEINS AND CASEIN FRACTIONS IN WATER AND VARIOUS SALT SOLUTIONS

Description of sample	pH values of caseins in water	pH values of caseins in various salt solutions		
		0.1N NaCl	0.1N CaCl ₂	0.1N NH ₄ Cl
<i>Bovine caseins</i>				
Whole "	5.10	4.95	4.80	5.05
α - "	4.90	4.70	4.50	4.80
β - "	5.30	5.20	5.05	5.30
<i>Buffalo's caseins</i>				
Whole "	5.15	5.00	4.90	5.10
α - "	5.00	4.80	4.60	4.90
β - "	5.30	5.25	5.10	5.30

products, which, however, show only minor differences amongst themselves. The pH of each product is seen to shift appreciably on the acid side in the presence of salts. This appears to be due to release of some of the H⁺ ions in exchange for binding of metal cations in the casein complex.

The pH titration curves of the various products on the addition of NaOH on the one hand and that

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 1 & 2. Titration curves of casein and casein fractions with hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide.

of HCl on the other, starting with isoionic point in each case, are plotted in Fig. 1 for bovine products and in Fig. 2 for buffalo's products. The differences in the various curves are of degree and not of kind. The α -caseins show much greater reactivity than β -caseins in the alkaline range while the whole caseins show intermediate behaviour in this regard. The differences in the reactivity in the acid range, however, are smaller. The titration curves, using calcium hydroxide and ammonium hydroxide as the alkalis (Figs. 3 and 4), also show the same essential features, the α -casein having higher base binding capacity

Fig. 3. Titration curves of bovine casein and casein fractions with calcium hydroxide.

than β -casein and the whole casein occupying the intermediate position. The titration curves of buffalo's caseins with these alkalis were also similar and are not given for reasons of space. The titration curves starting with acid solution at the lowest pH values and adding increasing amounts of alkalis were found to be identical with those plotted in Figs. 1 to 4.

The titration curves show two sharp points of inflection, one in the acid and the other in the alkaline range, irrespective of the nature of the alkali used as the titrant. This shows, incidentally, the merit of plotting pH against the amount of alkali bound and not the amount of alkali added to the protein. The first point of inflection occurs in the pH range 5.8–6.0 and appears to involve, largely, the neutralisation of phosphoric (first equivalent) and carboxylic acids. The second point occurs in the pH range 8.5–8.7 with NaOH and Ca(OH)₂ and 8.0–8.3 with ammonia and appears to involve neutralisation of imidazole, second equivalent of phosphoric acid and some of the amino groups etc. The amounts of alkalis neutralized at the two points of equivalence are recorded in Table 2. The following conclusions may be drawn :

- (i) Bovine products bind more of each alkali than buffalo's products do at each point of equivalence.
- (ii) α -caseins bind more of each alkali than β -caseins do. The values for the whole caseins lie in-between. Knowing that α - and β -caseins constitute roughly 60 and 40 per cent of whole casein¹⁶, the calculated values (given in parentheses) are seen to be in close agreement with

TABLE 2—AMOUNTS OF ALKALIES NEUTRALIZED AT THE TWO POINTS OF EQUIVALENCE

Description of sample	Sodium hydroxide (eq./10 ⁵ g casein)		Calcium hydroxide (eq./10 ⁵ g casein)		Ammonium hydroxide (eq./10 ⁵ g casein)	
	alkali neutralised at the first point	alkali neutralised at the second point	alkali neutralised at the first point	alkali neutralised at the second point	alkali neutralised at the first point	alkali neutralised at the second point
<i>Bovine Caseins</i>						
Whole casein	114 (119)	170 (172)	118 (117)	200 (201)	115 (117)	224 (228)
α -casein	126	188	128	222	128	250
β -casein	108	148	100	168	100	194
<i>Buffaloes's Caseins</i>						
Whole casein	110 (111)	169 (168)	116 (113)	192 (193)	113 (110)	208 (208)
α -casein	120	182	124	212	120	220
β -casein	97	148	96	164	95	180

the experimental values. This indicates absence of any interaction between major fractions of caseins amongst themselves when they are both present in the whole casein.

The titration curves are seen to extend upto about pH 2.0 on the acid side and 11.2 on the alkaline side. Thus as we add acid to casein, starting with its isoelectric point, the net positive charge on it increases gradually and attains, ultimately, a maximum value at about pH 2.0. Similarly, as we add increasing amounts of alkali, starting again with the isoelectric point, the net negative charge on the casein increases and attains, ultimately, a maximum value. These two extreme points, called the maximum 'proton charge' and maximum 'hydroxyl ion charge', represent the maximum acid and base binding capacities of the caseins. These values are given in Table 3. The corresponding values for α - and β -caseins (bovine products) reported by Hipp ¹⁰*et al.*, using sodium hydroxide as the alkali, are given in the parentheses.

It is seen that the acid values of our samples are appreciably higher. The alkali value of α -casein is fairly close to that of Hipp. However, the alkali value of β -casein is appreciably lower. The differences may be attributed to variations in climate, feed, heredity etc., involved in the two cases.

Fig. 4. Titration curves of bovine casein and casein fractions with ammonium hydroxide.

TABLE 3—MAXIMUM ACID AND BASE BINDING CAPACITIES OF CASEINS AND CASEIN FRACTIONS

Description of sample	Max. acid binding capacity (eq./10 ⁵ g casein)	Max. base binding capacity (eq./10 ⁵ g casein)		
		Sodium hydroxide	Calcium hydroxide	Ammonium hydroxide
<i>Bovine caseins</i>				
Whole casein	100	164	271	295
α -casein	110 (78)	194 (198)	312	342
β -casein	88 (68)	131 (150)	204	240
<i>Buffaloes's caseins</i>				
Whole casein	96	156	246	272
α -casein	105	180	282	316
β -casein	87	116	179	225

The buffaloes's caseins are seen to be deficient in acid as well as base binding capacity, as compared to the corresponding bovine products. The amount of alkali bound by a given casein varies with the nature of the alkali: the weaker the alkali, the greater the amount required to raise the pH value to 11.2. α -caseins are seen to be more active than β -caseins in the acid as well as the alkali range. The values for whole casein lie in between the two extremes and seem to fit in with the fact that it contains nearly 60 per cent of α - and 40 per cent of β -fraction. This again, indicates that the two major fractions of casein lie side by side, as separate entities, in whole casein without any significant chemical interaction with each other.

At the lowest pH value (2.0), the protein carries a net positive charge, as already stated, and all the acid groups, viz., phosphoric, carboxylic, sulphhydryl and phenolic are in the neutral state while the cationic groups, viz., guanidinium, imidazolium and amino carry positive charge. None of the groups are dissociated. However, as pH is raised gradually on the

Fig. 5. Titration curves of bovine α -casein in the presence and absence of formaldehyde.

addition of an alkali, the various groups start protonising in different pH regions, depending upon their respective pk values. The number of various side chain groups in a protein can, thus, be calculated from the titration curve, provided the pH range in which these groups ionise is known. The information in this regard has been made available in a previous publication⁹ from measurements of heats of ionisation at different pH values and is summed up below :

pH range	Groups neutralized
2.0— 6.5	Carboxyl+First equivalent of phosphoric acid.
6.5— 6.7	Imidazole
6.7— 8.4	Second equivalent of phosphoric acid.
8.4—11.2	α -amino, ϵ -amino, phenolic and sulphhydryl.

The number of amino groups can be obtained independently by another simple method. It is well known¹⁷ that in the presence of formaldehyde, the titration of these groups is essentially complete at pH 8.5 whereas hardly 5 per cent would be dissociated at this pH value in the absence of formaldehyde. Hence the difference in the amount of alkali bound at pH 8.5 in the presence and absence of formaldehyde gives the number of amino groups in casein. The titration curves of α -casein (bovine) in the absence and presence of 1 per cent formaldehyde are shown in Fig. 5. The two curves, as expected, superimpose in the pH range 2.0-6.5, since the groups involved in this range remain unaffected by the presence of formaldehyde. The deviations set in thereafter. The difference in the amount of alkali needed to raise the pH value to 8.5 in the presence and absence of formaldehyde gives the number of amino groups in the casein. Subtracting this value from the number of groups neutralized between pH 8.4 and 11.2, it is possible to obtain the number of phenolic and sulphhydryl groups separately from the amino groups.

The guanidinium groups are not neutralized even upto the maximum pH value, since their pk value lies beyond 12. It is possible, however, to determine these groups in another way⁵. The acid binding value gives, in fact, the number of imidazole+amino+guanidinium groups (say n). By subtracting the number of imidazole+amino groups (obtained from the titration curves as indicated above), from n , it is possible to obtain the number of guanidinium groups. To take an example, the value of n for α -casein (bovine) is 110 (cf. Table 3) while the sum of imidazole and amino groups is $19+68 = 87$ (cf. Table 4). Hence the number of guanidinium groups is equal to $110-87 = 23$, which, incidentally, is quite close to 25, the value reported by Gordon¹⁸ *et al* for the α -casein

The values of the various ionic groups present in the bovine as well as buffalo's products obtained following the procedure obtained above and presented

TABLE 4—EQUIVALENTS OF VARIOUS IONIC GROUPS PRESENT IN CASEINS AND CASEIN FRACTIONS

Description of Sample	Amounts of groups present eq./10 ⁵ g of casein						Total
	Side chain + α -carboxyl	Imidazole	Phosphate	$\alpha + \epsilon$ amino	Phenolic+ sulphhydryl	Guanidinium	
<i>Bovine Caseins</i>							
Whole Casein	94 (101)	18 (20)	29 (28)	60 (66)	38	22 (24)	261
α -Casein	110 (112)	19 (19)	32 (32)	68 (71)	48	23 (25)	300
β -Casein	87 (88)	20 (20)	23 (20)	48 (51)	19 (18)	20 (20)	217
<i>Buffaloes's Caseins</i>							
Whole Casein	90	17	26	56	32	22	243
α -Casein	100	17	29	66	43	22	277
β -Casein	82	19	19	48	14	20	202

in Table 4. The corresponding values for bovine caseins, obtained by analytical methods and available in the literature¹⁸, are given in the parentheses. The agreement in such cases is sufficiently close to permit the use of titration curves for estimating the various ionic groups in caseins and, may be, other proteins as well. The bovine products are seen to be richer than the corresponding buffaloes's products in almost all the ionic groups. The α -fractions are seen to be much richer than β -fractions. The values for the whole casein lie in between and it can be shown by simple calculation that these are sufficiently close to the values expected from its known α - and β -casein contents. These observations confirm that the two major fractions lie side by side in casein as separate entities without any significant chemical interaction with each other.

References

1. P. A. WILLIAMS and A. R. PEACOCKE, *Biochem. J.*, 1967, 105, 1177.
2. R. B. SCHEEL and M. A. LAUFFER, *Biochemistry*, 1967, 6, 3076.
3. J. J. BASCH and S. N. TIMASHEFF, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys* 1967, 118, 37.
4. E. BRESLOW and F. R. N. GURD, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1962, 237, 371.
5. C. TANFORD, *Advance Protein Chem.*, 1962, 17, 69.
6. I. G. F. GILBERT and N. A. MYERS, *Biochem et Biophys. Acta*, 1960, 42, 469.
7. W. F. HOFFMAN and R. A. GORTNER, "Colloid Symposium Monograph", Reinhold Publishing Corp., New York, 1924, 2, 209.
8. W. F. HOFFMAN and R. A. GORTNER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 769.
9. B. R. PURI, K. K. TOTEJA and R. C. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem., Soc.*, 1968, 45, 889.
10. N. J. HIPPI, M. L. GROVES and T. L. MCMEEKIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4822.
11. L. K. CREAMER, *Biochem et Biophys Acta.*, 1972, 271/2, 252.
12. R. C. WARNER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1725.
13. M. S. DUNN, *Casein Biochem. Preparations*, 1949, 1, 22.
14. N. J. HIPPI, M. L. GROVES, J. H. CUSTER and T. L. MCMEEKIN, *J. Dairy Sci.*, 1952, 35, 272.
15. C. TANFORD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 441.
16. D. F. WAUGH, M. L. LUDWIG, J. M. GILLESPIE, B. METTON, M. FOLEY and E. S. KLEINER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 4929.
17. H. NEURATH, "The Proteins", Academic Press, New York, 1964, 2, 171.
18. W. G. GORDON, W. F. SEMMETT, R. S. CABLE and M. MORRIS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3293.